

Geopolitical Tension in the Middle East: Repercussions on Education in the Kurdistan Region of Iraq

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Abstract

The Middle East has experienced several geopolitical instabilities, armed conflicts and humanitarian crises, and the effect of these geopolitical instabilities usually cause repercussions beyond borders affecting whole region including Kurdistan Region of Iraq (KRI). These beyond borders' repercussion causes deleterious impact on multiple sectors of the KRI including education. Currently, medical education in KRI has shifted to online and hybrid learning due to current tension between Iran and the United States of America and Israel from other side. Therefore, in this academic perspective, we aim to examine the impact of this geopolitical instability on medical education, and how it disrupted the traditional on-campus education in KRI.

Keywords: *Medical Education, Digital learning, Hybrid education, Geopolitical instability, Middle East, Iraq.*

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Introduction

In recent decades, the Middle East has experienced several geopolitical instabilities, armed conflicts and humanitarian crises. The current geopolitical tension between Iran from one side and the United States of America and Israel from other side has caused repercussions beyond borders, affecting neighboring countries including Kurdistan Region of Iraq (KRI) (Ali et al., 2025). The KRI infrastructure has been targeted by drones and missiles by Iran and its proxies, this has adversely affected the safety of academic staff and students in universities and schools. The education sector in the KRI has been frequently exposed to shocks which originated beyond its borders but had direct consequences on its education ("Kurdistan Region targeted," 2026). In this perspective, we aim to examine the impact of ongoing geopolitical tension in the Middle East on medical education in KRI. Furthermore, this paper explores how

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disruption of traditional on-campus education has led to a shift toward online education, and assessing psychological consequences of online education.

Disruption of Traditional On-Campus Education

One of the most noticeable impacts of the current crisis is the disruption of education in KRI, and medical education is not an exempt of this disruption. Medical institutions and facilities are already suffering from oversaturation and lack of resources (Hussein & Abozait, 2025; Hussein et al., 2026; Hussein & Mosa, 2025; Hussein, Naqid, & Mosa, 2026). The cross-border tension and attacks by drone and missiles have further stressed the impact on medical education and may have deleterious consequences if not managed carefully. Safety concerns led the Kurdistan Regional Government (KRG) to suspend or limit on-campus education. Such disruptions are often precautionary measures aimed at ensuring the safety of students, teachers, and administrative staffs (“Kurdistan Region extends,” 2026). However, such a suspension of classes may reduce effective instructional time, mutual understanding and active engagement of the students. Additionally, it also delays curriculum completion, and places pressure on academic calendar. Therefore, academic staff are required to compress and shorten the curriculum or move to accelerated teaching methods so they can cover the syllabus. Moreover, uncertainty about the whole educational process and unstable teaching environment creates psychological pressure among students, teachers, and parents, and may negatively impacts motivation and academic achievement of students.

Shifting towards Online and Hybrid Learning

Due to the safety concerns, medical colleges and institutions have adopted online education or hybrid learning. Such methods are necessary particularly during periods when physical attendance is deemed unsafe including wars and pandemics (Mosa, 2022). These adopted methods demonstrate degree of institutional adaptability and allow for the continuation of lectures, assessments, and academic communication even during crises. However, these methods may not suit medical education perfectly; since hand-on training is essential and vital for medical students, but online learning do not provide such opportunity for students, hence this may hinder students’ skill development and reduce the overall quality of training.

Furthermore, the shift to online learning exposes structural limitations within the educational system. Access to reliable internet infrastructure remains uneven across urban and rural areas, creating disparities in educational opportunity. Additionally, not all students have access to digital education gadgets and environment, further widening the gap between socioeconomic groups. Teaching staff and instructors may face challenges adopting digital and online methods particularly when interactive engagement or practical application is required. Moreover, monitoring online platforms, addressing student difficulties remotely, and managing curriculum adjustments are associated with psychological pressure that may contribute to professional burnout and reduce efficiency of teaching over time (Mosa et al., 2023).

Institutional Adaptation and Educational Resilience

Online and digital learning are not new and most of the teachers had good experiences with such methods of teaching during COVID-19 pandemic (Hussein et al., 2020). During COVID-19, medical institutions invested in digital infrastructure, educational platforms, and training programs for teacher in order to improve the quality of online education (Naqid et al., 2020). In the current crisis, the medical education system in the KRI has demonstrated notable resilience and adaptability. Shifting to online and digital learning shows balance between safety considerations and pedagogical effectiveness. It is suggested that policymakers should invest in international partnership and support programs that strengthen the educational system. Capacity building particularly in curriculum development and digitalization of the education is extremely important in ongoing uncertainty.

Recommendations

Given that digital and hybrid learning play a crucial role in sustaining the educational process during regional and global difficulties such as pandemics and wars; therefore, strengthening digital infrastructure in our region is essential. Consequently, we advocate for the followings: Universities should establish programs to continuously improve faculty, staff and student understanding of the application and adaptation of digital teaching modalities to boost the learning process during such uncertain periods. Additionally, policymakers should invest more in providing accessible and reliable electricity and internet connection and provide it at a reasonable price for students. Moreover, universities should ensure the quality of online and hybrid education through research and data collection to maintain academic integrity, educational standards, and guide evidence-based policy decisions. Finally, the mental health and psychological well-being of students and faculty is crucial, especially during such political uncertain period. Therefore, it is important that universities adopt online mental health services to assist students overcome anxiety, worry, and stress precipitated by the current situation.

Conclusion

Middle East crises have multifaceted impacts on the educational system in the KRI especially the medical education. Such impacts are evident in the disruption of on-campus education, and the psychological burden among teachers, students and parents. While such challenges pose a crucial impact on the educational system and academic outcome, they also promote the development of the institution and enhance its resilience. It is important mentioning that the long-term sustainability of medical education in KRI depends on the investment in the infrastructure of digital education and equitable access to teaching technologies. It's imperative to build resilient educational system able to respond to ongoing regional uncertainty.

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